

Ergonomic Design as a Determinant for the Prevalence of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders among Office-Based Civil Servants in Ondo State, Nigeria

O.E. Ayeni

Department of Occupational Therapy, Faculty of Medical Rehabilitation, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo City, Ondo State, Nigeria

D.O. Ibrahim

School of Public Health, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo City, Ondo State, Nigeria

A.T. Onigbinde

Department of Physiotherapy, Faculty of Medical Rehabilitation, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo City, Ondo State, Nigeria

G.O. Taiwo

Babcock University, Ilishan Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria

T.F. Kekere

Department of Prosthetics and Orthotics, Faculty of Medical Rehabilitation, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo City, Ondo State, Nigeria

S.C. Ayinla

Department of Prosthetics and Orthotics, Faculty of Medical Rehabilitation, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo City, Ondo State, Nigeria

I.V. Akpa

Department of Occupational Therapy, Faculty of Medical Rehabilitation, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo City, Ondo State, Nigeria

Abstract

Several reformations in the Civil Service have transformed the day-to-day activities in the sector from paper to the use of computer sets. However, the use of computer is characterized with high sedentary lifestyles and repetitive tasks among office-based workers, but there are limited studies conducted to evaluate the effect of this new working condition among civil servants. This study was conducted to investigate ergonomic design as a determinant of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders among Office-based Civil Servants in Ondo State, Nigeria. Ethical approval was obtained for this study. The study was a cross-sectional design using multistage sampling techniques to recruit 308 respondents. Structured and adapted questionnaires were used to assess ergonomic designs in offices and prevalence of pain. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 20, descriptive statistics was used for sociodemographic of respondents and Spearman rho's correlation coefficient was used to compare relationship between variables. Results were presented in tables and charts. Majority of the respondents were female, married and between the ages 30-34. The mean age of the respondents was 36.21 ± 8.75 years. 35 of the respondents were confounders and were exempted from completing the study on pain. There was 92.7%, 59.1% and 19.4% of 12 months, one week and point pain prevalence respectively among the 273 respondents that participated fully in the study. Most respondents have poor knowledge of ergonomics (61.9%) but 96.7% have good ergonomic practices (96.7%). There was no significant relationship between ergonomic design and prevalence of WRMSD ($r=0.090$, $p=0.136$), but there was a significant relationship between ergonomic practice and ergonomic awareness ($r=0.247$, $p=0.001$). Also, there was

More Information

How to cite this article: Ayeni OE, Ibrahim DO, Onigbinde AT, Taiwo GO, Kekere TF, Ayinla SC, Akpa IV. Ergonomic Design as a Determinant for the Prevalence of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders among Office-Based Civil Servants in Ondo State, Nigeria. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(4):118-29.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(4).16

Keywords:

Ergonomic designs,
Civil Servants,
Prevalence,
Work-related musculoskeletal
Disorders,
Ondo State.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

significant relationship between office ergonomic practice and prevalence of WRMSD ($r=-0.142$, $p=0.019$). Ergonomic design is not a determinant for the prevalence of WRMSD. However, the knowledge and correct practice of ergonomic among office-based civil servants can help to reduce the prevalence of WRMSD. Therefore, it is recommended that government should ensure the implementation of correct ergonomic practices in Civil Service. Also, government should provide regular trainings such as seminars and conferences on ergonomics for their workers.

Introduction

Background of the study

Civil Servants are the workforce of every nation, in Nigeria, they include all workers in government establishment except the military and police force [1]. According to United Kingdom Civil Service Commission [2], Civil Servants include professionals and career individuals in sectors such as health, education, agriculture, finance, works, sports, among others who are mostly on government payroll and have their offices in ministries or agencies of the federal, state, or local government secretariats depending on their job description and cadre. The civil service remains the bedrock on which government carry out its tasks and accomplishes its missions, they are usually the link for the maintenance of the executive arm of government [3]. To improve service delivery, civil service has undergone numerous reformations to promote service delivery among the civil servants. One of the recent developments in civil service was the introduction of computer workstations which has transformed civil service duties from paper to Electronic, leading to easier and faster delivery of service by Civil Servants [4]. However, like workers in other sectors, civil servants are as well prone to Civil Servants are as well prone to occupational hazards due to the scheme of their operations that requires long hours of sitting, writing and working on a computer set [3]. This working condition has predisposed civil servants has predisposed civil servants to a special type of occupational hazards known as Work Related Musculoskeletal Disorders (WRMD) [5]. Abdu, Ta, and Sulzakimin [6] defined Work Related Musculoskeletal Disorders as 'the injuries and pains which occur to office workers when exposed to various ergonomic risk factors in the office environment.' Therefore, Work Related Musculoskeletal Disorders is any form of pain or discomfort that an individual feel due to improper body positioning during work hours in the place of work. This can include low back pain, tendonitis, carpal tunnel syndrome, nerve compression, blood vessels compression, osteoarthritis and other related conditions. Work Related Musculoskeletal Disorder is the leading occupational hazard among civil servants or office workers and it is majorly due to the invention of computer system [7]. According to a study by Okezue, Anamezie, John and John, [8] showed that the signs and symptoms of Musculo-skeletal Disorders (MSDs) include body pain, paresthesia, hand stiffness, leg

swelling, eye redness, body weakness, tingling, and numbness. Studies have shown high prevalence of WRMSD among office workers, in a recent study conducted among 2934 Iranian workers, the study revealed high prevalence of WRMSD among female workers in the following order; back, shoulder, neck and upper limb [9]. In another study by Sweta, Ankit, and Shyam, [10], about 70% of the workers have one-year pain prevalence in body parts in the following order lower back, neck and upper back. In a study by Ritika & Pradeep, [11]. WRMSD is common among female workers than male subjected to the same working conditions and hours [12]. The prevalence of MSD and the affected region depends on the job descriptions of the individual and can be influenced by poor knowledge and awareness of ergonomics, poor compliance of Civil Servants with ergonomics [13]. Ergonomics is defined as the arrangement and design of workstation, tool, machine, equipment, and product with a cognizant consideration of human physical, psychosocial, biomechanical and physiological demand to enhance productivity and effectiveness work system with the assurance of safety, health and wellbeing of workers [14]. The aim of ergonomics is to make an individual (worker) comfortable on the job, ergonomics achieves this by simply fitting the job into the person's convenience and not having the person struggling to fit into the job [5]. By ergonomics, the way a workstation is fashioned is of utmost importance which include adequate lighting, spacious workspace, chair and tool design, positioning of both person and working tools [5].

Statement of the Problem

Work Related Musculoskeletal Disorder is among the highest contributor to adult rehabilitation and it has been established that over 1.7 billion individuals suffer WRMSD. This number is projected to increase in the next few years in low and middle-income countries, which Nigeria is included [14]. Moreover, Work Related Musculoskeletal Disorders among workers leads to low productivity, high rate of absenteeism and early retirement system [15]. Furthermore, some workers suffer from non-communicable diseases such as cardiovascular disease, obesity which is due to early retirement caused by WRMSD [16]. This causes a greater burden on the health care system of the country. The prevalence of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders among office based civil servants has been on the high rate due to poor

compliance with ergonomics [5]. In addition, Lyndall and Gabriele [17] established that there was a link between illness and workplace designs which is not always revealed until an intentional effort is taken to discover the linkage. However, previous studies did not investigate awareness and practice of good ergonomics among civil servants. Also, there is a dearth of adequate data on ergonomics and WRMSD among civil servants in Ondo State. It is on this note that this study investigated prevalence of WRMSD, awareness and practice of good ergonomics among office based civil servants in Ondo state.

Methodology

Respondents

The respondents for this study were office based Civil servants in Ondo state whose jobs duties are strictly administrative or secretarial. Civil servants who have spent a minimum of one year in services, were 18 years and above, whose job descriptions involve the use of workspace with computer sets were recruited for this study. However, Civil servants with previous history of pain due to sickness or injury, those pregnant and did not consent to this study were excluded.

Study Design

This study was a cross-sectional study.

Site of Study

This study was conducted in Akure, the Ondo State capital at the secretariat of the selected ministries which are Ministries of Work, Information, Health, Education, Finance and Economic Planning & Budget.

Sampling techniques

Respondents were recruited using a multi-stage sampling technique. This involves the following stages:

- First, the random selection of 6 of the 13 ministries in Ondo State, ministries with even numbers between 1-13 were selected.
- The second stage involved respondents who are willing to participate in the study (convenience sampling technique).

Sample Size Determination

The sample size was determined using the Fischer’s sample size formula for finite population [18] to recruit 308 respondents for this study.

Instrument

The study was carried out using both standard and structured questionnaires, the questionnaire for this study was divided into two parts which are Nordic questionnaire to assess pain prevalence and Ergonomic Questionnaires to assess the workstation design and ergonomic practice. Reliability study was conducted for the ergonomic questionnaire and Cronbach alpha coefficients obtained were, 0.860, 0.778, and 0.902 for ergonomics awareness, ergonomic design and practice respectively.

Procedure

Ethical Approval for the study was obtained from Health Research and Ethical Committee of the University of Medical Sciences, Ondo City, Ondo State. Detailed explanation and aim of the study were provided to respondents and informed consent was obtained from civil servants that fulfilled the inclusion criteria.

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using Statistical Pack for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Confidence interval and p value were set for 95% and 0.05 respectively. Descriptive statistics of percentages, pie charts and bar charts were used to describe sociodemographic variables. The relationships between variables were determined using Spearman Rho, correlation coefficient set at 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) to determine level of statistical significance.

Results

A total of 308 completed questionnaires were entered and analyzed, 35 respondents were confounders who could not complete the study on pain prevalence. Majority of the respondents were female, married, Christian and within the age group of 30-34 years, the mean age of the respondents was 36.21 ± 8.75 years. Also, the respondents are majorly from the Yoruba ethnic group. The respondents for this study are majorly from Ministry of Works who have spent 6-10 years in service and have obtained certificates from higher institution of learning and are mostly from the ministry of works. All the socio-demographic details are presented in figures 1-10.

Figure 1: Gender Distribution of Respondents

Figure 2: Age distribution of respondents

Figure 3: Marital Status of Respondents

Figure 6: Work Experience of Respondents

Figure 4: Religion Distribution of Respondents

Figure 7: Education Level of Respondents

Figure 5: Ethnicity Distribution of Respondents

Figure 8: Place of Work (Ministries) of the Respondents

Majority (92.7%) of the respondents have twelve months prevalence of pain prior to the study, more than half (59.1%) have one-week pain prevalence and there was 19.4%-point prevalence of pain at the time of the study. Low back pain (76.5%) was the most reported in the last twelve months and pain in one or both ankles (95.5%) was the least reported among respondents as represented in tables 1 and 2.

ministries provide training on the health implication of poor ergonomics at workplace. Also, some of the respondents (38.5%) were not aware of the meaning of ergonomics until the time of this study, while negligible percentage of the respondents (1.1%) were indifferent on the importance of attending seminars and conferences on ergonomics.

Table 1: Prevalence of WRMSD

PAIN QUESTION	YES	NO	TOTAL
Pain in any part of your body in the last one year	253(92.7)	20(7.3)	273(100)
Pain in any part of your body in the last 7 days	161(59.1)	109(39.9)	273(100)
Pain in any part of your body now	53(19.4)	220(80.6)	273(100)

Majority of the respondents (61.9%) have a poor knowledge of ergonomics in the workplace (Figure 9). As presented in tables 3-5, more than half of the respondent (52.7%) disagreed that their respective

Figure 9: Knowledge of Ergonomics

Table 2: Prevalence of WRMSD among Respondents (n=273)

	Pain (last 12 months)		Last 12 months pain preventing work		Pain in last 7 days with difficulty	
	Yes	NO	Yes	No	Yes	No
Neck	150 (54.9)	123 (45.0)	51 (18.6)	222 (81.3)	46 (16.8)	227 (83.1)
Shoulder	90 (32.9)	183 (67.0)	15 (5.4)	258 (94.5)	21 (7.6)	252 (92.3)
Elbow	27 (9.8)	246 (90.1)	6 (2.1)	267 (97.8)	6 (2.1)	267 (97.8)
Wrist/hands	35 (12.8)	238 (87.1)	6 (2.1)	267 (97.8)	16 (5.8)	257 (94.1)
Upper back	72 (26.3)	201 (73.6)	34 (12.4)	239 (87.5)	18 (6.5)	255 (93.3)
Low back	209 (76.5)	64 (23.44)	106 (38.8)	167 (61.1)	87 (31.8)	186 (68.1)
One or both hips/thighs	0	273 (100)	3 (1.0)	270 (98.9)	9 (3.2)	264 (96.7)
One or both knees	37 (13.5)	236 (86.4)	23 (8.4)	250 (91.5)	32 (11.3)	241 (88.2)
One or both ankles/feet	12 (4.3)	261 (95.5)	15 (5.4)	258 (94.5)	9 (3.2)	264 (96.7)

Table 3: Knowledge of Respondents on Ergonomics (n=273)

	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree
Ergonomics is a branch of office safety and health before receiving this questionnaire	6.5	14.7	2.2	38.1	38.5
The organization provides training to office workers concerning sitting and work posture in the office	7.7	7.7	0	46.2	38.5
Incorrect sitting posture while carrying out work causes body pains and work-related problems	38.8	45.4	2.2	9.2	4.4
The organization gives out periodicals, manuals or handbooks with guidelines on proper sitting/correct work posture	7.7	6.6	0	51.6	34.1
The organization engages the services of office/medical experts to educate workers on the health implication of incorrect posture of work	2.2	6.6	1.1	52.7	37.4
The organization has committee or any unit charged with the responsibility of educating workers concerning proper sitting posture during work	3.3	7.7	1.1	49.5	38.5
Attending seminars and conferences on office ergonomics help to learn about work posture and sitting position from time to time	25.6	46.9	1.1	4.4	22.0
Working for too long without break causes serious body pains and health related problems	38.1	55.3	2.2	0	4.4

Table 4: Opinion of Civil Servants on Ergonomic Designs of Workstations (n=273)

Variables	SA	A	N	D	SD
SEATING	84	110	3	31	45
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Backrest adequately supporting lower back	54(19.8)	109(39.9)	3(1.1)	64(23.4)	43(15.8)
Seat wide enough to accommodate me	36(13.2)	91(33.3)	3(1.1)	91(33.3)	52(19)
Seat front is comfortable and doesn't pinch my knees	24(8.8)	78(28.6)	15(5.5)	95(34.8)	58(21.2)
Seat is well cushioned and comfortable for sitting	36(13.2)	78(28.6)	6(2.2)	95(34.8)	58(21.2)
Armrests wide enough and do not interfere with movement	24(8.8)	78(28.6)	15(5.5)	104(38.1)	52(19)
KEYBOARD AND INPUT DEVICE					
Keyboard is stable and large enough	54(19.8)	201(73.6)	6(2.2)	9(3.3)	3(1.1)
Mouse is located next to keyboard (without reaching) on same level	54(19.8)	201(73.6)	6(2.2)	9(3.3)	3(1.1)
Mouse is easy to activate, not too large or too small.	60(22)	207(74.7)	3(1.1)	0(0)	3(1.1)
Wrists & hands do no rest on sharp or hard edges	48(17.6)	141(51.6)	6(2.2)	54(19.8)	24(8.8)
MONITOR					
Screen is at the same level with the eyes/face	128(46.9)	133(48.7)	0	9(3.3)	3(1.1)
Users with glasses can read without moving head up and down	15(5.5)	46(16.8)	0	137(50.2)	75(27.5)
Monitor distance permits reading without moving forward or back	15(5.5)	39(14.3)	0	135(49.5)	84(30.8)
Monitor position is directly in front of user	86(31.5)	154(56.4)	0	27(9.9)	6(2.2)
Glare (light from computer screen) is not a problem	12(4.4)	24(8.8)	3(1.1)	135(49.5)	99(36.3)

Table 5: General Opinion on General Work Area and Accessories (n=273)

WORK AREA					
Sufficient space between desk / keyboard tray and thighs	15(5.5)	75(27.5)	6(2.2)	118(43.2)	59(21.6)
Legs and feet have sufficient clearance under work surface	12(4.4)	60(22.0)	6(2.2)	127(46.5)	68(24.9)
ACCESSORIES					
Document holder is stable and large enough to hold materials	18 (6.6)	24(8.8)	3(1.1)	159(58.2)	69(25.3)
Document holder is placed on same height as monitor	3 (1.1)	27(9.9)	3(1.1)	171(62.6)	69(25.3)
Wrist / palm rests keep arms, wrists, and hands straight and in-line.	24 (8.8)	84(30.8)	9(3.3)	104(38.1)	52(19)
Telephone can be used with head upright and shoulder relaxed.	43(15.8)	200(73.3)	9(3.3)	9(3.3)	15(5.5)
GENERAL					
Workstation & equipment can be adjusted for good working posture.	24(8.8)	18(6.6)	9(3.3)	155(56.8)	67(24.5)
Workstation, components, & accessories maintained serviceable	39(14.3)	68(24.9)	9(3.3)	128(46.9)	28(10.3)
Computer tasks organized to allow varied tasks with other activities	21(7.7)	91(33.3)	9(3.3)	90(33.0)	62(22.7)

Keys: SA: Strongly Agree A: Agree N: Neutral D: Disagree SD: Strongly Disagree

Figure 10 showed that most of the respondents have good ergonomic practices in their offices with a rate of 96.7%. Table 6 presented the results on ergonomic practices among respondents, it was shown that most of the respondents (79.4%) strongly agreed to taking a walk after a prolonged sitting.

There was no significant relationship between Ergonomic design and prevalence of WRMSD ($r=0.090$, $p=0.136$), but there was a significant relationship between Ergonomic awareness and practice ($r=0.247$, $p=0.001$). Also, there existed a significant relationship between office ergonomic practice and prevalence of WRMSD and a weak but negative correlation ($r=-0.142$, $p=0.019$) as shown in tables 7-9.

Figure 10: Ergonomic Practice of Respondents

Table 6: Ergonomic Practice in Offices among Civil Servants (n=273)

Variables	Always n (%)	Sometimes n (%)	Rarely n (%)	Never n (%)
How often do you put the following into practice?				
Keeping head and neck straight and in-line with body alignment when sitting	160 (58.6%)	107 (39.1)	6 (2.1)	0
Keeping head, neck, & trunk facing forward toward keyboard and monitor	106 (38.8)	152 (55.6)	15 (5.49)	0
Keeping trunk perpendicular to floor or leaning backward into backrest when sitting	72 (26.3)	186 (68.1)	12 (4.3%)	4 (1.4)
Keeping neck, shoulders, & upper arms straight with torso (other body parts from neck to waist) while on seat	105 (38.4)	159 (58.2)	6 (2.1)	3 (1.0)
Keeping upper arms & elbows close to body and extending outward/inward	137 (50.1)	121 (44.3)	12 (4.3)	3 (1.0)
Keeping forearms, wrists, & hands straight and in-line with body	130 (47.6)	137 (50.1)	6 (2.1)	0
Keeping wrists & hands straight, not bending, in or out, up/down	119 (43.5)	115 (42.1)	24 (8.7)	15 (5.4)
Keeping thighs parallel to the floor or slightly elevated above knees	76 (27.8)	149 (54.5)	27 (9.8)	21 (7.6)
Keeping feet resting on floor or stable footrest	50 (18.3)	100 (36.6)	64 (23.44)	59 (21.6)
Keeping wrists and hands straight and in-line when typing	91 (33.3)	146 (53.4)	19 (6.9)	17 (6.2)
Keeping head upright and shoulder relaxed when using telephone	100 (36.6)	155 (56.7)	12 (4.3)	6 (2.1)
Taking a walk to stretch body after a prolong sitting	217 (79.4)	47 (17.2)	9 (3.2)	0

Table 7: Relationship between Ergonomic Design and Prevalence of WRMSD (n=273)

		ERGONOMICS		WRMS
Spearman's rho	ERGONOMICS	r	1.000	0.090
		p	.	0.136
	PREVALENCE	r	0.090	1.000
		p	0.136	.

Table 8: Relationship between Ergonomic Practice and Awareness (n=273)

		Awareness	Practice
AWARENESS	r	1	0.247
	p		0.001
PRACTICE	r	0.247	1
	p	0.001	

Table 9: Relationship between Ergonomic Practice and Prevalence of Musculoskeletal Disorder (n=273)

		PRACTICE	MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDER
PRACTICE	r	1	-0.142
	p		0.019
MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDER	r	-0.142	1
	p	0.019	

Table 10: Prevalence of pain among confounders (n=35)

PAIN QUESTION	YES	NO
Pain in any part of your body in the last one year	35(100)	0(0)
Pain in any part of your body In the last 7 days	18(51.4)	17(48.6)
Pain in any part of your body now	7(20.0)	28(80.0)

Table 10 presented the result of the 35 confounders, there is a hundred Percent twelve months prevalence of pain among them, seven days prevalence of pain (51.4%) and 20% point prevalence of pain.

Discussion

The finding of this study is similar to a study conducted in Sokoto state where majority of the respondents were female and average age of the respondents been 36.99±8.23 years [19]. However, this is in contrary to the report of a study conducted among office workers in Kano State where majority of the respondents were men and average age was 38.6±9.6 years [20]. This study corroborated the findings of Metgud [12] where WRMSD is highly reported among female commercial bank workers in Lagos. Also, this result supported the findings of Yun et al., [21] among commercial bank workers in South Korea where there was a higher prevalence of WRMSD among women in the sector more than men. Thus, women are more predisposed to work-related musculoskeletal disorders than their male colleagues in the work place [11]. Although no specific reason was given for this high prevalence of WRMSD among women but it can be assumed that it may be due to the female anatomy and physiology which most of them at that age were within their reproductive cycle and thus are actively involved in delivery labour and parenting, thereby stretching some parts of the body [22]. Also, it might be due to higher percentage of women among the target population [23]. The findings of this study depicted a 92.7%, 59.1% and 19.4% of twelve months, one week and point prevalence of WRMSD respectively among respondents. The most reported body parts in descending orders were low back, neck, upper back, shoulder and thigh. This is similar to the findings of a study carried out in Malaysian where back, shoulder and neck were highly reported among administrative university of staff [24].

The high prevalence of low back pain (76.5%) prevalence in this study is similar to another study conducted in Iran among office workers with 72% and 52% for low back and neck pain respectively [9]. This result also supported the finding of Salihu et al., [20] in a study conducted in Northern Nigeria among Office based Civil Servants in Kano with 70% pain prevalence of the low back. However, most of the respondents in Salihu et al’s study were men which may be due to religion and cultural belief in the region. Similarly, this study also corroborated the findings of a study among office-based workers in Lagos with pain prevalence of the low back at seventy one percent [25]. This finding is also closely related to the findings of a study conducted among Civil Servants in Germany with 60% low back pain prevalence [26]. However, the findings of this study contradicted the findings of Omokhodion., et al., [27], among Civil Servants in Oyo State with low back pain prevalence at 38%. Also, the result of this study is higher than the findings of Spyropoulos, *et al.*, [28] among six hundred Civil Servants in Greek. Furthermore, it was observed that the findings of this study contradicted the results of similar study conducted among bankers in Lagos where neck pain was the most reported at 80% [12]. This study also contradicted a comparative study done among computer and non-computer office workers with pain prevalence at 64% among computer users [29]. It was noted that the findings of this study were far lower than the findings Omojunikani *et al.*, [30] in a survey carried out among oil workers in Nigeria where low back pain was reported at 90%. Although that study was carried out among heavy skilled workers and not office based who used computers. This is a pointer for future study to repeat this study among workers in other sectors in other regions of the country. Also, the findings of this study contradicted the findings of the study in South

Korea by Yun *et al.*, [21] where Neck and shoulder were the most reported body pain. Majority of the respondents (96.7%) were satisfied with their workplace design and were able to perform their daily tasks with much convenience and satisfaction, this is similar to the findings of Nwaogazie, Omuruka and Adaramola, [5] where they explain ergonomic design as one that enables comfortability and satisfaction by civil servants while performing their duties. This also corroborated the findings of similar study in India where it was found that the way an office workspace is designed has an effect on the performance of task in the place of work [15]. However, it was noted that despite the poor level of ergonomic awareness (61.9%), there was high level of ergonomic practice (96.7%) among the respondents. This may be due to the level of educations of the respondent since majority of the respondents are graduates from tertiary institution of learning, since most of the respondents obtained certificates from tertiary institutions. Although no study has been conducted to compare the level of education and ergonomic practice among office workers, but the findings of this study showed a relationship between the two variables. Similarly, the good level of ergonomic practice despite poor awareness may also be due to lengthy years in service, that is, over the time, many of the respondents have been able to decide posture that is most convenient for work even if there was no evidence-based training for such practice. Also, previous study has not been conducted to compare the relationship between years of experience and ergonomic practice among office-based workers. Furthermore, the high prevalence of WRMSD among female respondents maybe due to difference in the level of ergonomic prevalence since there existed a relationship between gender and ergonomic practice [31]. The findings of this study showed there was no significant relationship between ergonomic design and prevalence of WRMSD among respondent. However, this contradicts similar study conducted in India where there was a relationship between ergonomic design and WRMSD [10]. This probably maybe due to difference in level of technological advancement in the two countries, since the present study was conducted within the range of available technological level in Nigeria. This study also contradicted the findings of similar study conducted in Iran [9]. However, it was worthy of note that those studies did not consider the opinion of the respondents on the computer accessories used as done in this study. For instance, many of the respondents in this study (74.7%) were satisfied with the size of the mouse and keyboard, this is most likely because that is the commonest keyboard and mouse that they have ever seen in the country. However, there existed relationship between ergonomic practice, awareness and prevalence of

WRMSD. This is similar to the findings of Oana-Ruxandra, *et al* [32] in a study conducted among IT professional where there existed a relationship between ergonomic practice and prevalence of WRMSD. This finding is also supported by a survey carried out in Malaysia among administrative staff in a University where ergonomic awareness is associated with the prevalence of WRMSD [24]. Also, it can be deduced that the high level of low back pain in this study maybe due to lack of adjustable features in the workstations since more than half of the respondents disagreed on the availability of adjustable back rest, making many of the respondents assume most convenient posture while typing (ergonomic practice), thereby leading to prevalence of low back pain in this study. This supported the findings of Dennis, [33] in a comparative study carried out among industrial workers in United States where working conditions is related to high level of WRMSD among the workers.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the high prevalence of WRMSD among respondents in this study is not due to ergonomic designs of workstations.

References

- [1] Habeeb IP. "New Service Tenure - Oronsaye, FCSC Boss ClashOver Exams" (2009). Daily Trust. Available at: <https://allafrica.com/stories/200910261383.html>
- [2] United Kingdom Civil Service Commission. What is a civil servant? Archived from the original on 11 October 2019.
- [3] Alamina FE, Douglas KE. Musculoskeletal Symptoms Among Computer Users: A Comparison Between Bankers And Administrative Civil Servants In Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *Gazette of Medicine*, 2019;7.
- [4] Okezue OC, Anamezie TH, Nene JJ, Okwudili JD. Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders among Office Workers in Higher Education Institutions: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Ethiop J Health Sci*. 2020 Sep;30(5):715-724. doi: 10.4314/ejhs.v30i5.10
- [5] Nwaogazie1 IL, Omuruka TC, Adaramola SS. Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders: A Case of Office-Based Civil Servants in Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Tropical Disease & Health*, 2016;18(1):1-13. doi: 10.9734/IJTDH/2016/27544
- [6] Abdu G, Ta SW, Sulzakimin M. Creating office ergonomic awareness among the staff of Katsina State Local Government offices in Nigeria: A viable strategy for reducing the prevalence of work related musculoskeletal disorders. *International Journal of Research and Review*. 2017 4(1) 31 -48
- [7] Briggs AM, Woolf AD, Dreinhöfer K, Homb N, Hoy DG, Kopansky-Giles D, Åkesson K, March L. Reducing the global burden of musculoskeletal conditions. *Bull World Health Organ*. 2018 May 1;96(5):366-368. doi: 10.2471/BLT.17.204891

- [8] Okezue OC, Anamezie TH, Nene JJ, Okwudili JD. Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders among Office Workers in Higher Education Institutions: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Ethiop J Health Sci.* 2020 Sep;30(5):715-724. doi: 10.4314/ejhs.v30i5.10
- [9] Fariborz MS, Forouzan G. Prevalence and patterns of work-related musculoskeletal disorders among bankers in Maiduguri, Northeast Nigeria. *Occup Med Health Aff.* 2018;2:3. doi: 10.4172/2329-6879.1000169
- [10] Sweta P, Ankit PV, Shyam P. Prevalence and Determinants of Musculoskeletal Disorders among Information Technology Sector Employees of Ahmedabad, Gujarat. *Journal of Comprehensive Health,* 2020;8(2). doi: 10.53553/JCH.v08i02.006
- [11] Ritika MS, Pradeep. Prevalence of work-related musculoskeletal disorders among IT professionals in India-a literature review. *International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences,* 2020;8(10):3765. doi: 10.18203/2320-6012.ijrms20204271
- [12] Metgud S. Work-related Musculoskeletal Health Problems among the Information Technology Professionals in India: A Prevalence Study". *International Journal of Management Research and Business Strategy.* 2018;2(2): 118-127.
- [13] Jeffrey EF. *Ergonomics in workplace,* 1995; 13(4).
- [14] Hartvigsen J, Hancock MJ, Kongsted A, et al. What low back pain is and why we need to pay attention. *Lancet.* 2018 Jun 9;391(10137):2356-2367. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(18)30480-X
- [15] Jasmine M, Vinoth GC. Healthy workplace with ergonomics among software engineers: a review. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health,* 2019 Oct;6(10):4605-4610. doi: 10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20194535
- [16] Williams A, Kamper SJ, Wiggers JH, O'Brien KM, Lee H, Wolfenden L, Yoong SL, Robson E, McAuley JH, Hartvigsen J, Williams CM. Musculoskeletal conditions may increase the risk of chronic disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis of cohort studies. *BMC Med.* 2018 Sep 25;16(1):167. doi: 10.1186/s12916-018-1151-2
- [17] Strazdins L, Bammer G. Women, work and musculoskeletal health. *Soc Sci Med.* 2004 Mar;58(6):997-1005. doi: 10.1016/s0277-9536(03)00260-0
- [18] Jung SH. Stratified Fisher's exact test and its sample size calculation. *Biom J.* 2014 Jan;56(1):129-40. doi: 10.1002/bimj.201300048
- [19] Awosan KJ, Yikawe SS, Oche OM, Oboirien M. Prevalence, perception and correlates of low back pain among healthcare workers in tertiary health institutions in Sokoto, Nigeria. *Ghana Med J.* 2017 Dec;51(4):164-174.
- [20] Salihu M, Lawal MM, Abuhuraira AM, Abdullahi Y, Umar M, Oruche CA, Jacob JA, Muhammad F. Prevalence of low back pain and associated factors among office workers in Kano city, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Orthopaedics,* 2021;7(5):907. doi: 10.18203/issn.2455-4510.IntJResOrthop20213375
- [21] Yun MH, Lee YG, Eoh HJ, Lim SH. Results of a survey on the awareness and severity assessment of upper limb work-related musculoskeletal disorders among female bank tellers in Korea. *Int J Ind Ergon.* 2001;27(5):347-57. doi: 10.1016/S0169-8141(00)00062-7
- [22] Khalid A, Ambreen S, Syeda Tali. Ergonomic Awareness: Simple Solution To Prevent Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders (WMSDs). *Journal of Bahria University Medical and Dental College,* 2019.
- [23] Evim AC, Ulku KS, Sinan A. The investigation of work-related musculoskeletal disorders among female workers in a hazelnut factory: Prevalence, working posture, work-related and psychosocial factors. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics,* 2019;74:102838. doi: 10.1016/j.ergon.2019.102838
- [24] Fazilah AA, Nur AN. The impact of risk factors associated with long-term computer use on musculoskeletal discomfort among administrative staff: A case study. *Journal of Modern Manufacturing Systems and Technology,* 2022;6:7-17. doi: 10.15282/jmmst.v6i2.8557
- [25] Okezue OC, Anamezie TH, Nene JJ, Okwudili JD. Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders among Office Workers in Higher Education Institutions: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Ethiop J Health Sci.* 2020 Sep;30(5):715-724. doi: 10.4314/ejhs.v30i5.1
- [26] Hoy D, Bain C, Williams G, March L, Brooks P, Blyth F, Woolf A, Vos T, Buchbinder R. A systematic review of the global prevalence of low back pain. *Arthritis Rheum.* 2012 Jun;64(6):2028-37. doi: 10.1002/art.34347
- [27] Omokhodion FO, Sanya AO. Risk factors for low back pain among office workers in Ibadan, Southwest Nigeria. *Occup Med (Lond).* 2003;53(4):287-9.
- [28] Spyropoulos P, Papathanasiou G, Georgoudis G, Chronopoulos E, Koutis H, Koumoutsou F. Prevalence of low back pain in Greek Public Office Workers. *Pain Physician.* 2007;10(5):651-60.
- [29] Village J, Rempel D, Teschke K. Musculoskeletal disorders of the upper extremity associated with computer work. *Occup Erg.* 2006;5:205-18.
- [30] Omojunikanbi OA, Akinpelu AO, Ekechukwu END. Prevalence, pattern and predictors of work-related musculoskeletal disorders among oil workers in Nigeria. *Work.* 2022;71(1):151-163. doi: 10.3233/WOR-205005

[31] Sonia SA, Sabina A, Rosa PS. Musculoskeletal disorders risk assessment methods: a scoping review from a sex perspective. *Ergonomics* 2023;0:0, pages 1-17.

[32] Oana-Ruxandra S, Mihaela O, Corina P, Bogdan A, Nicoleta M, Alexandru B, and Claudiu A, Assessment of Forward Head Posture and Ergonomics in Young IT

Professionals – Reasons to Worry? *Med Lav* 2023; 114 (1): e2023006. DOI: 10.23749/mdl.v114i1.13600

[33] Dennis RJ. The relationship between working conditions and musculoskeletal /ergonomic disorders in a manufacturing facility – a longitudinal research study. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 2015;3:4480 – 4484.

